

Active Control of Transverse Viscoelastic Damping in the Tectorial Membrane: a Second Role for Outer Hair Cells?

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Abstract.

In two-dimensional (2-D) box models of the cochlea, the ratio of transverse velocity gradient to basilar-membrane (BM) velocity scales with the wavenumber that sharply increases approaching the wave peak. As a result, transverse viscosity damping could play an important role in the short-wave region of the traveling wave. Recent models have emphasized this stabilizing role of viscosity which counteracts the spatial increase of BM velocity. In parallel, observations from optical coherence tomography (OCT) have described a gradient of velocity in the outer hair cell (OHC) region [Cho and Puria, *Scientific Reports*, **12**, 18715 (2022)]. We hypothesize that OHC activity, combined with tectorial membrane (TM) structural properties, can oppose the gradient of velocity within the TM, canceling TM transverse viscous damping. This mechanism would give the cochlea the ability to modulate viscous dissipation in the short-wave region, thereby shaping the nonlinear traveling-wave response. Based on a formal approach, we show that the removal of transverse viscous forces would imply a conversion from transverse to radial mode of deformation in the TM. With further assumptions about the coupling between the TM and the BM, we derive a formula for the viscous load on the BM in both passive and active scenarios. We use a transmission-line model and the WKB method to simulate traveling waves in response to tones at different stimulation levels. The calibration of the model is partly based on OCT data from mice, including data on TM motion. Our simulations show that by modulating the viscous load, the peak magnitude of the wave can be controlled by up to 7.5 dB. The inclusion of a more classical anti-damping term is necessary to achieve maximum effect and to capture the full dynamic range of the response gain. With the textbook view of OHCs acting directly on the BM under re-evaluation in light of recent OCT data, the control of viscous damping in the TM emerges as a viable candidate for a second mechanism governing active cochlear mechanics.

INTRODUCTION

The healthy mammalian cochlea is characterized by a compressive growth of its mechanical response to tones as the stimulus level is linearly increased [1, 2, 3, 4]. The decrease in gain has alternately been interpreted as indicative of the amplification of low-intensity traveling waves (e.g. [5, 6]), or as evidence of the compression of higher-intensity waves [7]. The exact mechanisms involved in this nonlinear process — also called the “active process” of the cochlea [8, 9] — are partly unknown or still under debate, although it is widely accepted that the electromotile outer hair cells (OHCs) play a critical role [6, 8, 9, 10]. A commonly cited mechanism underpinning the active process is the push-pull action of OHCs. This mechanism suggests that the cell bodies of the OHCs contract when the BM goes up, in response to well-timed hair cell deflections caused by shear motion between the tectorial membrane (TM) and the reticular lamina (RL). As a result, OHCs would exert a pulling force on the basilar membrane (BM), amplifying its upward motion [9, 11]. However, recent experimental data, including observations from optical coherence tomography (OCT) [2, 4, 10], have described unexpected patterns in cochlear micromechanics. These patterns appear at odds with the apparent simplicity of the push-pull action of OHCs, leaving room for alternative, less direct explanations of the active process [12, 13].

This paper introduces the hypothesis of a second role for OHCs in controlling transverse viscoelastic damping occurring in the TM. This mechanism corresponds to the idea of a ‘friction control’ within the cochlea, capable of modulating the gain of the mechanical response, as anticipated by some authors [14]. The hypothesis presented in this paper, however, originated from two other recent works. The first described a transmission-line model including two opposing 2-D hydrodynamic effects: ‘fluid focusing’ and viscous dissipation [15, 16]. Both effects are wavelength-dependent and increase in strength in the short-wave region. As the traveling wave approaches its peak, the wavelength is reduced, but so is the characteristic height of the pressure wave [9]. As a result, the fluid motion becomes increasingly focused around the BM region, with a simultaneous increase of transverse velocity gradients and

associated viscous stresses. This work highlighted the potential role of viscosity in stabilizing the traveling wave in the short-wave region and provided a simple mathematical framework to include this effect in a 1-D transmission-line model. The second study presented OCT data showing the existence of a velocity gradient in the OHC region during auditory stimulation in live gerbils [17]. The authors showed that the part of the RL above the innermost row of OHCs moved with around 10 dB lower magnitude than the part above the second row of OHCs. This observation was valid on a wide range of frequencies around the characteristic frequency (CF).

Our premise is that the radial gradient of transverse velocity observed in the OHC region is generated to modulate transverse deformation in the TM, thus affecting viscoelastic loss in the TM mechanically coupled to the organ of Corti and BM. In this paper, we explore the consequences of this hypothesis, first with a formal analysis carried out under simplifying assumptions, then using a 1-D transmission-line model implemented in the frequency domain to simulate traveling-wave responses at different sound levels. This simplified modeling approach allows us to present an overview of important ideas related to the proposed mechanism, without addressing every micromechanical or biophysical aspect of how it could be implemented in the cochlea.

METHODS

Proposed mechanism

We consider that the TM is a nearly incompressible material (Poisson ratio close to 0.5), allowing viscous stresses to be expressed as $\boldsymbol{\tau} = \mu_{TM} [\nabla \mathbf{v} + (\nabla \mathbf{v})^T]$ where μ_{TM} represents the dynamic viscosity of the TM and $\nabla \mathbf{v}$ is the gradient of velocity. To simplify the analysis, we only consider the transverse components of the velocities — and the transverse derivatives of the (transverse) velocities for the gradients. We further assume that the TM has a rectangular shape (not consistent with drawing) with the lower and upper surfaces parallel to the BM (i.e., orthogonal to the transverse direction).

Figure 1 shows a schematic of the hypothesized velocity gradients and associated viscous forces at play in the passive and active scenarios. We omit any consideration of phase at this point. 1) *Passive case* (Fig. 1 left): In the short-wave region, and in absence of OHC activity, we assume that the velocity in the TM follows the same decreasing trend in the transverse direction as in the rest of the fluid. When the BM moves up, this results in a gradient of velocity $\nabla \mathbf{v}$ directed downwards. To simplify, we consider that the motion is characterized by an irrotational flow, so that the viscous stress tensor has zero divergence within the TM. In this case, there is no contribution of viscous forces in the bulk of the TM, but the TM is still subject to two viscous forces acting on its lower and upper surfaces, equal to: $2\mu_{TM}S_{TM}\nabla \mathbf{v} \cdot \vec{n}$. In this formula, S_{TM} is the area of the lower/upper surface for the longitudinal section under consideration, and \vec{n} is a unitary vector normal to the surface pointing in the direction of the TM body. We neglect the viscosity of the scala media fluid, which is several orders of magnitude smaller than that of the TM [18]. On the lower surface, the viscous stress gives rise to a damping force $2\mu_{TM}S_{TM}\nabla v$ opposite to the BM velocity (v_{BM}). Conversely, on the upper surface, it generates an anti-damping force equal to $-2\mu_{TM}S_{TM}\nabla v$. However, as motion decreases when one moves further away from the BM, this force is of lower magnitude than the first force acting on the lower surface, resulting in a net damping effect.

2) *Active case* (Fig. 1 right): we consider that the activity of the OHCs results in a gradient of transverse velocity in the region of the OHCs mechanically coupled to the TM via the OHC hair bundles. Our assumption is that this gradient can counteract the gradient of fluid velocity inside the TM. This is visually represented by the blue and orange arrows with opposite increasing trends on the diagram. This situation would lead to negligible transverse velocity gradient, and consequently, negligible transverse viscous stress, in the TM. At this stage of the description, one might have noticed a potential inconsistency: the reasoning implies that the OHCs have an effect on the transverse gradient of (transverse) velocity, while observations in the OHC region demonstrate a radial — not transverse — gradient of (transverse) velocity. This apparent discrepancy could be explained by the arrangement of radially-oriented collagen fibers within the TM, which exhibit a downward inclination (Ref. 19, Fig. 1; Ref. 20, Fig. 11) or even a more pronounced turn towards the BM approaching the marginal zone (Ref. 21, Fig. 1). Since the collagen fibers provide more mechanical support compared to the softer gel-like matrix of the TM, the role of this configuration could be to orient the gradient of velocity generated by OHC activity towards the transverse direction.

FIGURE 1. Diagram of hypothesized transverse velocity vectors (thick arrows), velocity gradients (thin blue and orange arrows) and viscous forces (red arrows) associated with an upward motion of the BM for a cross-section of the cochlea. In the passive case (left), a downward velocity gradient generates opposing viscous forces on the lower and upper surface on the TM, eventually leading to a net viscous damping. In the active case (right), transverse viscous loss is eliminated due to the cancellation of the transverse-velocity gradient within the TM. This cancellation would result from the effect of OHC activity (blue arrows) counteracting the ‘natural’ fluid velocity gradient (orange arrows).

Deformation modes in the TM

Several implications of the proposed mechanism can be inferred by trying to characterize the motion of the TM in the passive and active scenarios. We consider that the TM impedance is dominated by mass and viscosity at frequencies near CF in the marginal region. We assume that the flow in the TM is incompressible and irrotational, characterized by a pressure field satisfying Laplace’s equation. Recent studies have emphasized the importance of longitudinal motion in the region of OHCs *in vivo* [4, 22]. Accordingly, we consider that the coupling of the TM with the OHC region via the hair bundles drives longitudinal oscillations in the TM, proportional to the real part of $\exp(j(\omega t - kx + \phi))$. In a cross-section of the cochlea, the assumptions presented above lead to $\Delta p = k^2 p$, where Δ is the 2-D Laplacian — formally the same equation as for the fluid above the BM in a 3-D box model. Solving this equation is hard because it depends on the geometry of the TM and on the pressure or velocity fields in the surrounding fluid. However, a reasonable approximation in the short-wave region and the marginal zone of the TM could be $p(r, z) \propto \exp(-k_z z) \exp(-k_r r)$. In this expression, the decrease along the transverse direction mirrors the exponential decrease of fluid pressure above the BM. The exponential term for the radial direction accounts for the outward radial motion of the TM when the BM moves up. Laplace’s equation further implies that $k_z^2 + k_r^2 = k^2$. In the passive case, we assume that $k_z = k_r = k/\sqrt{2}$. This corresponds to the hypothesis that radial and transverse deformations are mainly driven by the longitudinal deformations, and ignoring any factor of anisotropy. A second justification is the observation that radial and transverse velocity in the TM, related to the first derivatives of the pressure field, are almost identical in magnitude in the short-wave region at high sound levels (Fig. 2C). In the active case, our hypothesis suggests that the transverse deformation in the TM is reduced. Therefore, we introduce a second mode of motion with no transverse gradient of (transverse) velocity, characterized by: $p(r, z) \propto (z_0 - z) \exp(-k_r r)$. This time, the radial and transverse velocity are uncoupled, and the incompressibility is expressed by $k_r = k$. The action of the OHCs can be interpreted as a conversion of deformation in both directions into radial deformation alone, a consequence of the near-incompressibility of the TM.

OCT data of TM motion *in vivo* is scarce due to the low reflectivity of the TM. However, Lee et al. [3] provided data of TM motion in the mouse that could be consistent with the existence of two deformation modes in the short-wave region (reproduced in Fig. 2, top panel). At high sound levels, in the region 7 kHz to 10 kHz (for CF=10 kHz), the radial and transverse motions of the TM present the same magnitude on average (Fig. 2C). But this observation does not hold at lower sound levels. The analysis presented above predicts that the radial motion at low sound levels is still related to the derivative of the pressure field, proportional to $k_z = k$, higher than in the passive case by a factor $\sqrt{2}$. Assuming that the ratio of local pressure to BM velocity remains the same, irrespective of the sound level, this agrees with the observed enhancement of radial TM motion over transverse BM motion at low sound levels, in the region where amplification is thought to occur (Fig. 2A).

FIGURE 2. Top: OCT vibration data from Lee et al. [3] (**A.**, **B.**, **C.**): displacement ratios in response to tones at one cochlear place (CF=10 kHz) averaged from $n=6$ CBA/CaJ mice. Ratios for both radial (subscript R) and transverse (subscript T) motions in 10-dB steps are presented. Standard errors (error bars) are shown for the lowest and highest sound levels. **Bottom: D.** Lumped-element model for the local BM impedance. In addition to the harmonic oscillator elements (right part), the impedance includes a variable negative resistance, a current generator (simulating the vibration ‘hotspot’ of the OHC region), and a variable resistor modeling viscous damping from the TM load. The parameters a and G (not homogeneous to mechanical resistance) in blue are the main variables. **E.** The parameter a controlling the viscous load varies as a function of frequency and sound level (light to dark blue). At a given sound level, $a(f/CF)$ is a sigmoid loosely fitting the displacement ‘boost’ in panel A.

Mechanical model and BM admittance

To derive a formula for the BM admittance in both passive and active scenarios, we start by considering a simplified model of cochlear micromechanics with two degrees of freedom (DoF). One DoF is the transverse velocity v_{BM} and the second is the transverse velocity of the reticular lamina v_{RL} . The latter is assumed to be identical to v_{TM} , consistent with the motion between the TM and RL being essentially radial [23]. In the absence of TM viscous load, we still assume the presence of a classical anti-damping term, corresponding to a negative resistance in the BM impedance (Fig. 2D). To incorporate the viscous forces acting on the TM in the BM admittance, we make the strong assumption that these forces do not exert work on the RL in the reference frame of the BM. This assumption is valid if OHC electromotility compensates for all the viscous load from the TM, so that the quantity $v_{RL} - v_{BM}$ remains of constant amplitude irrespective of the amount of viscous damping. Conceptually, this translates into modeling the action of OHCs as a ‘velocity generator’, akin to a current generator in an electrical analogy (Fig. 2D). The consequence of this assumption for the 2 DoF model is that the viscous forces acting on the TM are entirely transferred to the BM mass with velocity v_{BM} . We do not specify the mechanical coupling between the RL and BM beyond this assumption. In the model version presented here, we take this simplification one step further by considering that v_{TM}/v_{BM} remains constant across stimulus frequency, essentially reducing the model to 1 DoF.

To evaluate the viscous force F_V acting on the TM in the passive case, we use the analysis of deformation modes that was presented in the previous subsection. By letting v_{TM} be the transverse velocity of the lower part of the TM, the exponential decrease in the passive mode gives $\frac{\partial u_z}{\partial z} = -k_z v_{TM}$ on the lower surface of the TM, while on the upper surface, it yields: $\frac{\partial u_z}{\partial z} = -k_z e^{-k_z H_{TM}} v_{TM}$, where H_{TM} is the height of the TM. From these two relations, and considering the simplified geometry described earlier, we obtain $F_V = -2\mu_{TM} S_{TM} (1 - e^{-k_z H_{TM}}) k_z v_{TM}$ for the viscous force acting on the TM. In the simplified mechanical model we introduced, the viscous force acting on the TM is transferred to the BM with the same magnitude. Therefore, the new viscous term can be included in the equation of a harmonic oscillator to obtain the following BM admittance (see Ref. 15 for a similar derivation):

$$Y_{BM} = -\frac{j\omega}{\sigma_{BM}\tilde{\Delta}} \text{ with } \tilde{\Delta} = -\omega^2 + j\omega \left[\Gamma + 2\frac{\mu_{TM}}{\sigma_{BM}} (1 - e^{-k_z H_{TM}}) k_z \frac{S_{TM}}{S_{BM}} \frac{v_{TM}}{v_{BM}} \right] + \omega_{BM}^2. \quad (1)$$

Numerical simulations

We follow the same approach as in Sisto et al. [15], where a WKB method was used to simulate the frequency response of a 1-D transmission-line model including 2-D hydrodynamics effects, i.e., fluid focusing and transverse viscous damping. Defining $\overline{p_d}$ as the averaged differential pressure between the upper and lower scalae in a cross-section of the cochlea, the transmission-line is characterized by the equation:

$$\frac{\partial^2 \overline{p_d}}{\partial x^2} = -Z_f Y_{BM} \alpha \overline{p_d} = -k^2 \overline{p_d}, \quad (2)$$

where Z_f is the fluid impedance, Y_{BM} is the BM admittance and k is the wavenumber. α is a correcting factor to account for the fluid focusing effect. It is computed with the approximation $\alpha = \frac{kH}{\tanh kH}$ derived for a 2-D box model, where H is the height of the cochlea. From the wave equation (Eq. 2) and BM admittance formula (Eq. 1), we find the dispersion relation:

$$k^2 = \frac{2\alpha\omega^2\rho}{\sigma_{BM}H \left(\omega_{BM}^2 - \omega^2 + j\omega \left[\Gamma + 2a \frac{\mu_{TM}}{\sigma_{BM}} (1 - e^{-k_z H_{TM}}) k_z \frac{S_{TM}}{S_{BM}} \frac{v_{TM}}{v_{BM}} \right] \right)}. \quad (3)$$

Here, we introduced a parameter a ranging from 0 to 1 to quantify the strength of the viscous damping from the TM load. $a = 1$ corresponds to the passive mode, $a = 0$ corresponds to the fully active mode, and intermediate values represent linear combinations of both modes. In the right-hand side of the equation, α and k_z both depend on k . To derive a value for the wavenumber, we used the same recursive procedure described in Sisto et al., empirically converging for the range of values of interest for the simulation of the traveling wave.

The same numerical values as the WKB model in Sisto et al. were used to simulate the traveling wave (Ref. 15, Table II). In particular, we considered that Γ , the damping factor in the absence of TM viscous load, is the sum of a passive and active term, i.e., $\Gamma = \Gamma_p + \Gamma_a$ with $\Gamma_p = \omega_{BM}$ and $\Gamma_a = -G\omega_{BM}$. The numerical values for the additional parameters were: $\mu_{TM} = 150 \text{ mPas}$ [18], $k_z = k/\sqrt{2}$, $H_{TM} = 25 \mu\text{m}$, and $S_{TM}/S_{BM} = 0.25$. To simulate responses at different levels of stimulation, we considered several versions of the linear model, each with different effectiveness of the active mechanism, approximating the response of the system at a given stimulus level. Three parameters were varied simultaneously: v_{TM}/v_{BM} , G (representing classical negative damping), and a (controlling the viscous damping from the TM load). The two first parameters remained constant across frequencies, while a was modeled as a sigmoid function of ω/ω_{BM} . The three parameters were loosely adjusted using the Lee et al. data [3]. The functions $a(\frac{\omega}{\omega_{BM}})$ (shown in Fig. 2E) were chosen based on the regions of enhancement of the ratio displacement TM_R/BM_T (Fig. 2A). v_{TM}/v_{BM} was linearly decreased from 3 to 1.7 as sound level increased from 10 to 80 dB, based on Fig. 2B. G was linearly decreased from 1.05 to 0.95 to reproduce the dynamic range of the BM response; $G = 1$ representing the state where the traveling wave experiences no gain or loss of power (in the absence of TM viscous load). Note that we do not take into account any phase difference between v_{TM} and v_{BM} in the current model.

RESULTS

Figure 3 shows simulation results for a 10-kHz probe roughly representing the responses from 10 to 80 dB SPL (in 10-dB steps) in mice. The upper panel shows the spatial spreads of the responses (gain). For the full model (Fig. 3C), the real part of the wavenumber (not shown) was 16 mm^{-1} at the peak, corresponding to a wavelength of 0.4 mm, consistent with experimental values [24]. The modulus $|k|$ (not shown) remained nearly constant across sound levels (variation of less than 1% at the peak), in line with the findings of Sisto et al. [15]. By contrast, the phase of k became increasingly negative with higher sound levels, indicating a shift towards more dissipative states. We show this trend in the lower panel of Fig. 3 with the phase of jY_{BM} , aligning with the phase of k in the short-wave region or k^2 in the long-wave region [15]. The plots on the left show the responses when the TM viscous load stays in the passive mode. For comparison, we also show the responses without TM viscous damping (paler lines), but including the viscous fluid stress on the BM [15] (with water viscosity $\mu_w = 1 \text{ mPas}$) to ensure stability. Comparing these two sets of responses demonstrate the stronger effect of the TM viscous load compared to cortilymph viscosity at the BM surface. To achieve a comparable effect to the passive TM viscous load, one would need to increase the fluid

FIGURE 3. Simulations of the WKB model: response to a tone ($f_p = 10$ kHz) at various stimulus intensities. x refers to the place on the cochlear partition. **Top:** Magnitude of v_{BM} normalized to BM velocity at the base of the cochlea ($x = 0$). **Bottom:** Phase of jY_{BM} for the same responses. Left panel (A., D.): Only the negative damping term is linearly varied, from $G = 1.05$ to $G = 0.95$. Responses in blue correspond to the TM viscous load in the passive mode. Responses without TM viscous load but with inclusion of viscous fluid stress on the BM are shown with the paler lines. Center panel (B., E.): Responses with a fixed G factor but with the TM viscous load varying as indicated in Fig. 2 E. Right panel (C., F.): Both G and the viscous damping are varied. In all panels: the vertical gray line corresponds to the cochlear place where $\omega_{BM} = 2\pi f_p$.

viscosity to $4.5\mu_w$, with the $b = 2.5$ correction factor explained in Sisto et al. [15] (not shown). The main effects of viscosity align with those observed by Sisto et al.: improving the system stability and reducing the spatial shift of the wave peak. The center panel in Fig. 3 corresponds to the reciprocal simulation settings, where the negative damping factor G is kept constant, but the TM viscous load is modulated according to Fig. 2E. In these simulations, v_{TM}/v_{BM} was kept to 3 to show a maximal modulation effect. The two sets of plots demonstrate that the impact of the modulation depends on the negative damping term. Under power amplification ($G = 1.05$), the wave peak occurs in the short-wave region where the effect of viscosity is stronger, resulting in a large modulation of the peak (up to 7.5 dB gain difference between the extreme conditions). The effect is significantly reduced if the peak occurs before the wave reaches the short-wave region (2-dB gain difference for $G = 0.95$). In the simulations with the full model shown in the right panel, negative damping and modulation of viscous load combine to generate a large gain peak in the most sensitive state. This is achieved while preserving a small difference in gain outside the peak region across sound levels, and maintaining a limited spatial shift of the peak (1/3-octave assuming scaling symmetry).

This paper introduced the hypothesis of an active control of the viscous load on the BM via cancellation of transverse deformation in the TM. Several arguments of different nature were provided in support of this hypothesis. The central argument was the possibility that transverse velocity gradients predicted by 2-D box models could be compensated by velocity gradients in the region of OHCs observed experimentally. Secondary arguments included structural or mechanical properties such as the orientation of collagen fibers in the TM, as well as vibration data potentially corresponding to two deformation modes in the TM in the region basal to the peak. However, these arguments are only indirect and do not prove that the mechanism is actually implemented in the cochlea. The simulation of traveling waves with realistic parameter values shows that the proposed mechanism in theory could have a sufficient effect on BM velocity within the peak region. But the derivation of the model was based on many assumptions and simplifications, which tends to downplay the conclusions. One crucial assumption is that the magnitude of motion in the TM follows an exponential decrease in the short-wave region in the passive case, similar to the fluid flow above the BM in simple models of the cochlea. Simplifications were made for many other relevant aspects: the geometry of the TM, the nature and direction of the flow (e.g., assumption of irrotational flow), the coupling between the TM and BM, etc. More realistic models could help refine the conclusions of this simplified approach in future investigations.

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COMMENTS AND DISCUSSION

[Christopher Shera]: Thank you for this very interesting paper. The proposed “second role” for OHCs is intriguing, but to understand it better, I need some more help interpreting Fig. 1, which explains (I think) the basic idea of the model. I think I understand the “passive” panel. But in the “active” panel I have some questions:

- Are the “faded orange” arrows supposed to represent the “passive” velocity gradient from Fig. 1? (They are the same size and color). If not, what do they represent? (The caption says they represent the “natural” gradient, but I don’t understand what “natural” means here.) Why are the arrows now faded (i.e., what do you intend to convey by that)? Perhaps the faded orange arrows are supposed to represent the velocity gradient in the active case but when the collagen fibers are absent?
- Why does the size of the blue arrows in the TM increase with distance from the bottom surface of the TM? Is that somehow a consequence of the radial gradient in the OHC region transformed by the variable orientation of the collagen fibers?
- More generally, I don’t understand the two velocity gradients (faded orange and blue) that are assumed to cancel.
- Does your model predict that the upper surface of the TM moves less than the lower surface in the passive case, but that their transverse motions are more similar in the active case? Is this an experimental prediction you could mention? How should mutations that affect the collagen fibers change this prediction?

[François Deloche] (author) : Thank you Prof. Shera for your questions!

- Yes you are correct that the faded orange arrows represent the transverse gradient from the passive case. I call it ‘natural’ since it corresponds to the decreasing trend of fluid velocity when moving away from BM, which is found in many simple models (e.g., 2-D box model). But perhaps the word ‘natural’ is a bit of a reach. In the subsection following the description of the proposed mechanism, I suggest instead that this gradient could be a consequence of longitudinal deformations in the TM driven by the organ of Corti. In any case, the existence of a decreasing trend in TM transverse velocity similar to fluid velocity above the BM (in the passive case) is a key assumption of the model.
- The orange arrows are faded in the active case as we assume that they do not correspond anymore to the actual gradient. Instead, they represent one of the two ‘contributions’ to the transverse gradient. The second one is, as you described it, the contribution from the deformation in the OHC region (blue arrows) rotated by the particular orientation of the collagen fibers (radial gradient transformed in a transverse gradient). These two contributions tend to cancel each other. The arrows representing the different ‘contributions’ are helpful for visually explaining the mechanism, but it does not mean that the velocity field can actually be decomposed into these two components. It is probably more accurate to see the proposed mechanism as favoring a mode of TM motion without transverse deformation, as it is described in the section on the deformation modes.

I hope these points clarify Fig. 1. On your last question, yes it is a prediction of the model that the upper surface of the TM moves less transversely than the lower surface (in the passive case), in the short-wave region. The difference is not very large, though: in our simplified model, around 1.5 dB at the peak for the full passive mode (‘dead’). In the most sensitive case, after the traveling-wave peak where ‘amplification’ does not occur, this difference can go up to around 4 dB. Regarding the mutant mice with altered TM properties, I am not sure about the micromechanics but I am planning to see if the model can generate predictions that are consistent with previous experimental findings (on hearing thresholds, etc.).

[Alessandro Altoè]: you write that you have a 1-D model but your admittance is actually from a 2-D model, is that correct?

[François Deloche] (author) : The way I see it is that it is a 1-D model with a correction including the fluid focusing effect, since the model builds on the dispersion relation from Sisto et al. 2021.

[Alessandro Altoè]: If it includes the alpha factor from that paper, then it is equivalent to a 2-D model.

[François Deloche] (author) : Alright, then it is a 2-D model!

[Robert Raphael:] I am curious if that model has something to say about the RC time constant. Because you have a 'second' mechanism that tries to compensate for the viscosity at the surface of the TM, for this you need OHCs to work in an extended high frequency range, so it could make the RC problem worse.

[François Deloche] (author) : I am not familiar enough with the literature on OHCs and the RC problem to answer precisely the question. But from what I understood, it is possible that the OHCs still compensate for the viscous load after the roll off associated with the RC time constant.

[Sunil Puria]: Can you clarify why in your last figure all your plots peak well before the characteristic place?

[François Deloche] (author) : The vertical line corresponds to $2\pi, \omega_{BM}$, the local resonance frequency appearing in the admittance formula. But because of viscous damping, the traveling wave is damped long before it reaches that place, so the peak found at a more basal location. The same observation was made in Sisto et al. 2021.

[Renata Sisto] (author) : We found indeed that the wave peak occurs in the region where the wavenumber is still real or has a small phase, so well before the 'nominal' characteristic place. This is due to the stabilizing force of viscosity, which gets large when the wavenumber increases.

[Julien Meaud]: Isn't that because you used a 2-D model, in which the fluid adds a mass to the basilar membrane? This reduces the frequency of the peak, and it is what we see in FEM models. It is also similar to the description by C. Steele of the focusing of the fluid in the short-wave region: it increases the effective mass of the cochlear partition, therefore lowering the effective characteristic frequency at each place.

[François Deloche] (author) : I don't know if it is strictly equivalent, here the alpha correction factor accounting for fluid focusing is in the numerator of the BM admittance, not in the denominator. In our model, I believe the lowering of the characteristic frequency is rather due to the viscous term in the denominator.

[Renata Sisto] (author) : For the fluid focusing effect, it is indeed equivalent to the description of Charles Steele of a reduction of the inertia of the fluid involved in the traveling wave. But I prefer to see the fluid focusing as an effect that boosts the local pressure at the level of the BM. It seems more direct to me.